

Ensuring Sustainability of Public Pharmaceuticals Supply Chain SYSTEMS in East Africa: A Case of Ethiopia

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Sustainability of Pharmaceuticals Supply chain Management systems is found to be a prime importance as the governments are, at least, in the contemporary world, particularly in developing horizons are expected to provide public goods to their citizens.

To this effect, states are struggling to set up health sector delivery systems to deliver their mandate as duty bearers to their citizens. However, the business continuity of these service delivery organs of several governments are at stake due to their undeterminable future at the bare face of everchanging business environment, sky-rocketing prices due to inflations and fiscal, macro & micro economic policies, tense world trade and global conflicts and the like. Not only providing services but also ensuring their continuity for an unforeseeable future remains a challenge.

Therefore, this study is dedicated to exploring the possibilities for sustainability of pharmaceuticals supply chain system in developing countries with specific reference to Ethiopia. To facilitate the process, the study delved into the sustainability of supply chain systems and financial sustainability as its cause and effect.

To gather input for the study of PSM & Financial Sustainability of service delivery entities, several assessments and analyses had been conducted through survey observations, field visits, key informant interviews, and extensive document reviews. The areas selected for observation were purposefully chosen based on their stakeholder relationships, levels of interaction, and intentions to enhance future collaboration. Notable visits included the Afar Regional Health Bureau, Dubti General Hospital, EPSS Samera Hub in the northeast, Arbaminch Hub of EPSS, Arbaminch General Hospital, and the Gamo Zonal Health Department in southern Ethiopia. In Addis Ababa, we contacted ALERT Hospital, Lebu Health Centre, and the AA #1 Hub of EPSS, engaging all functions and directorates within the EPSS Hub. During these visits, key informants were interviewed using pre-designed questions, and warehouses were inspected to observe processes.

Furthermore, the consultant conducted a SWOT analysis based on the collected information, as well as a review of reports, policies, financial statements, and audit opinions. A validation session was also facilitated. This process identified additional performance metrics to measure financial sustainability, assess the current situation, identify potential gaps, and establish goals within these metrics. This strategic approach will enable the institution to make progress toward financial sustainability while considering future financial needs, mandated service levels, and best practices from peer countries.

The SWOT analysis highlighted the need for improvements in logistics coordination, cost minimization, productivity enhancement, risk management, and asset utilization, while also revealing significant growth potential and opportunities.

Considering perceived strengths and opportunities around, supported by evidence obtained by application of various financial modelling and trend analyses, to address perceived weaknesses and identified gaps, we recommend strategies focused on revenue diversification, cost minimization, productivity enhancement, and overall performance improvement. Proposed

initiatives include skill development programs, on-the-job coaching, the development of manuals and standard operating procedures (SOPs), revisions to policies and procedures, process improvements, and investments in upgrading and utilizing fixed assets, liberalizing the organ to develop and implement research-based business models and exercise autonomy to design robust workforce acquisition, retention and development systems including salary scale decisions. To ensure the continuous supply system, financial sustainability must be ensured by taking all available opportunities around, including partnerships and short-term subsidies with observed political will, and use competitive advantage of existing huge strength and momentum.

To facilitate the implementation of these proposed strategies and detail activities, a detailed multi-year operational and financial sustainability plans need to be developed, and realized accordingly.

CONTEXT of the Study

As defined by Camara and Chato in (Sustaining Your NGO's Mission: A Roadmap to Financial Sustainability | Humentum). Financial sustainability means a nonprofit can maintain the resources it needs to develop, deliver, and expand on its mission over the long term while minimizing financial risk and maintaining autonomy. Ensuring financial continuity allows your organization to deliver its services and programs without interruption.

The failure experience of Public Pharmaceuticals Supply system is a bare fact in Africa. Which dictates the need for utmost endeavours of ensuring its continuous supply.

Besides, these days, public pharmaceuticals supply systems, are highly leveraged by aids in one or other forms in the realm of tremendous cut in aids as evidenced by the recent decision to close USAID. However, developing self-sustaining system for such services and enabling them to remain in public service with minimum external financial support found to be a prime importance. In this respect, governments continue to advocate for increased commitments, to ensure that such lifesaving services are provided and owned as public.

These, coupled with the growing demand for supply and distribution of quality medical supplies, pharmaceuticals, and other essential inputs, require positioning such government organs for a more financially sustainable future. These background settings demand states strategically address at a optimum effort.

“The application of the principles of strategic planning is what has shaped the world in communities and businesses that have delivered the history of achievements accomplished by humanity. Use of strategy has caused the rise and fall of nations and organizations’. Strategic planning is a universal tool that combines knowledge, skill and wisdom.” *World Bank Guideline for Public Entities DSP final.adj

However, stability, consistent positive performance, and the goal of financial viability and resource adequacy along with global price scalation remain challenges of such institutions.

States' commitment for ensuring uninterrupted supply chain of pharmaceuticals in their respective areas of influence had be exhibited to be huge as it was emphasized globally as set out in the strategic document of WHO below among others.

- To improve health services through better governance, financing, staffing and management, informed by reliable and accessible evidence and research Indicators and targets
- Reduction in the coverage gap for an integrated set of interventions and services in at least eight out of 10 countries

“The staggering trend of public Pharmaceuticals Supply system dictates the importance of ensuring its continuous service delivery.”

“The findings prove that the SOEs of an emerging country could reach financial sustainability only if the government ownership is below the threshold.”

Major Objective of the study

- To advise strategic recommendation to ensure sustainable pharmaceuticals supply chain in East African countries

Sub objectives of this study focus on:

This study is aimed at

- identifying underlying factors for the effective performance of supply chain systems in developing world, like Ethiopia.
- exploring available opportunities,
- understanding and considering existing internal strengths and capabilities,
- identifying logistical, technical, and policy gaps in quest of ensuring long term service delivery.
- Ultimately, it is to suggest viable strategic interventions needed to ensure uninterrupted supply service, enabling the provision of affordable, equitable and reliable medical services.

Methodologies:

This study employed descriptive research involving mixed approach of qualitative and quantitative research modalities.

Sampling and Tools:

The areas selected for observation were purposefully chosen based on their stakeholder relationships, levels of interaction, and intentions to enhance future collaboration. Engaging all functions and directorates within the public supply chain system, adequate number of in-depth observation and documentary reviews were conducted.

During these visits, key informants were interviewed using pre-designed questionnaires.

To achieve the study's objective survey method had been used to get first-hand information from relevant practitioners in the field of pharmaceutical supply chain in the public sector entities in Ethiopia.

Participants were selected using non-probability sampling, specifically purposive sampling, supplemented by snowball sampling until information saturation was reached. Purposive sampling was based on participants' knowledge and involvement in EPSS operations. From the organizations identified in the desk review, key informants were selected based on their functions and understanding of EPSS operations. A total of 17 participants were identified, although 7 were unable to participate due to time and logistical constraints. Table 2 provides a breakdown of the various categories of key informants. Additionally, committee members involved in specific components, such as the Three-Year Plan preparation committee, were approached for insights. Their ongoing situational assessments contributed valuable information for baseline determination. Technical advisors to EPSS leadership also played a crucial role in compiling relevant data for planning and status evaluation.

Furthermore, consultations were held with the Human Resources, Internal Audit, General Services, Reverse Logistics team, and advisors to the Director General to deepen operational knowledge of the service.

Data Validation

Qualitative research methods were employed to gather the views of key informants who were intimately involved in day-to-day operations at EPSS. From all walks of the service from head quarters, through the HFs. The participants were called from different functions of the EPSS.

Situation analyses

A SWOT analysis of the Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Supply Service (EPSS) reveals that its renowned expertise in process development has been significantly bolstered by substantial investments from various partners, the government, and its workforce. This strength should be fully leveraged to capitalize on opportunities identified in several assessments.

Like any organization, EPSS faces threats that necessitate proactive measures to counteract competition from other actors, particularly in the private sector, as well as challenges posed by prevailing market conditions and socio-economic, geopolitical, and policy environments.

Adoption of various strategies are needed, such as revisiting its business model to gain greater autonomy in setting a workable structure, designing attractive compensation systems, and transforming its organizational structure. Additionally, integrating digital architecture into its processes is essential for operating effectively in a contemporary and dynamic environment. From these perspectives, the situational analysis is expected to yield multiple benefits for the EPSS.

The findings discussed in this document impact not only the Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Supply Service (EPSS) but also all supply chain stakeholders, from the Ministry of Health (MOH) and program units down to the smallest clinics and hospitals. The consultant's systemic findings include issues related to administration, policy, management, and performance measurement. These key areas need strengthening to enable EPSS to become the leading national and East African supply chain agency as outlined in its Pharmaceuticals Supply Transformation Plan II (PSTP II).

I had also conducted assessments and analyses through

- observations,
- field visits,
- key informant interviews,
- and extensive document reviews including company reports.
- SWOT, scenarios, trend, Ratio analyses, financial modelling, and simulations; as well as a review of performance reports, policies, financial statements, and audit reports were made.
- Two Validation sessions were also facilitated and industry practices from peer countries were reviewed.
- Thus, this critical process review aimed at exploring potential viable strategies which could ensure sustainable public or state-owned supply chain services for pharmaceuticals, medical supplies and equipment.
- Ultimately, such study results are expected to contribute to the body of literature in the sector.
- As we study, it is attempted to review and analyze governance system of Ethiopian pharmaceuticals supply service (EPSS). The study also used the critical path analysis of the entire processes from forecasting, quantification, through procurement, transiting, clearance, to the last-mile delivery of pharmaceutical commodities to the customers.
- In the process, several econometrics were used to determine system efficiency, conversely system in-efficiencies, slack capacities.
- On the other hand, working policies, procedures, and directives were also studied to see their relevance, workability and the like. The effect of political will, considerations and actions to such state organs engaged in public goods provision are also examined.
- As a contrast, sector industry has been scanned by using the five-forces analysis model to see how the market operates. While SLEPT analysis is conducted to gauge the Service's level of social acceptability, public obligation, and compatibilities to multi-dimensional expectations.
- Finally, the SWOT analysis report describes the contemporary strengths, weaknesses hovering threats and reap opportunities to the Service under study.
- The entity's contribution and performance need to be monitored to evaluate its performance against the objectives of its establishments and mandates.

Literature Review

2.1. Prior Studies on SOEs

Previous research on SOEs has mainly focused on comparing the financial performance of SOEs and private firms, especially profitability and efficiency. Some studies report no

significant difference in financial performance between the two. For example, **Kole and Mulherin (1997)** surveyed 17 companies and found that their financial performance did not differ between periods of private ownership and partial or full U.S. government ownership. Likewise, **Omran (2004)** examined 54 newly privatized Egyptian companies with a matching number of state-owned enterprises between 1994 and 1999. Again, they found no significant difference in financial performance between the two groups of entities. However, other studies report a different picture. **Boardman and Vining (1989)** compared all companies registered in Norway and reported that private companies significantly outperformed state-owned companies in terms of return on assets and cost relative to sales revenue. **Boardman and Vining (1989)** compared 500 non-US industrial firms, including private firms and some or all state-owned firms and found that, in a competitive environment, private firms were more profitable and productive than state-owned firms. **Dewenter and Malatesta (2001)** also showed that private companies are significantly more profitable than state-owned companies by comparing Fortune 500 companies. Similar results were recently reported by **Phi et al. (2021)** when they surveyed 25,000 companies worldwide. Many studies use agency theory to explain SOE performance (Mbo and Adjasi 2017). Agency theory assumes that agents gain their benefits at the expense of their principles (Boko and Qin 2011).

Some researchers have pointed out that other government interventions can also adversely affect financial performance. Examples include the government's requirement of SOEs to promote the national agenda (Wisuttisak and Rahman 2021), the need to satisfy competing stakeholders' needs (Mbo and Adjasi 2017), the appointment of politically affiliated individuals as high-ranking officers (Wisuttisak and Rahman 2021) or inflexible human resources policies to prevent unemployment (Boko and Qin 2011).

2.2 Existing theories around Supply chain Management (SCM).

As Rota et al. puts organization can implement several strategies in their endeavor for sustainable business operations. "Strategies for cost reduction are diverse and can be implemented in various ways to help businesses reduce operating costs. Developing a cost reduction plan that outlines specific goals and strategies can help keep cost reduction efforts focused and measurable. SCM encompasses all activities that take place from raw material acquisition to the delivery of the finished product or service to the end customer. Research indicates that Japanese companies have implemented various strategies for cost reduction in supply chain management (SCM) relating to exports and imports. One of the key strategies is supplier management. Japanese companies have established long-term relationships with suppliers to ensure stable and reliable supply of goods and services. These relationships are based on mutual trust, cooperation, and collaboration. The study concluded that Japanese companies can implement several strategies to achieve cost reduction in their SCM processes related to exports and imports. These strategies include supplier management, streamlining transportation, lean manufacturing, outsourcing, supply chain automation, inventory optimization, collaborative planning, standardization, sustainable SCM, risk management, continuous improvement, cross-functional collaboration, multi-modal transportation, and data analytics. Risk management strategies can help companies mitigate risks in SCM processes and minimize costs associated with disruptions or delays. It is crucial for companies to assess their SCM processes and identify the strategies that are most suitable for their unique requirements. The study recommended that companies should consider implementing multi-modal transportation methods to optimize their supply chain operations."

2.3. Prior Studies on Financial Sustainability:

Putra described Financial Sustainability in Rota et al. (2023), as it means whether an SOE can continue to operate without government subsidies (Putra et al. 2021). Rota et al. (2023) observed that sadly, very few studies have investigated the issue. Nonetheless, the issue is essential. and continued "For example, the Minister of Finance of South Africa, in his 2018

budget speech, recognized that the business models of some SOEs are unsustainable, and their capital structures are too reliant on debt.”

Also stated that any company’s financial sustainability are measurable. As He mentioned “The Australian Local Government Association (2006) suggested that measures of financial sustainability should consider an entity’s ability to repay its present and future obligations. This view is supported by Amani and Fadlalla (2015), who wrote that future earnings and sales growth are essential to achieving financial sustainability.”

Accordingly, the study results are depicted in the findings section below.

Per the analysis, we use functional departments of the entity as a study object to ensure a deep dive cross sectional assessment and inter-temporal progresses over the span of ten years

Logistics issues	Policy framework	Asset Utilization Issue	Supply Chain Performance Measurement and Management issues
High down time of existing fleet capacity High cost of repair and maintenance Poor coordination & planning in resource use Mismatch of skill-job	Limited authority to negotiate and attract competent workforce, the proclamation dictates the application of Civil service commission principles. Blanket HR procedure without considering job nature,	Enhance productive efficiency of incinerators Maximizing revenue generation schemes Excess Cash Management	Significant expiry and stock outs are experienced partially due to forecasting inaccuracies, Significant procurement Lead time Need for proactive planning and coordination in clearing & transit to minimize high demurrage costs,
Plan the use of unused and partially used Infrastructure and facilities	Revised EPSS statues, policies, guidelines/ SOPs. Efficiency metrics for staff performance	Inter-organizational communication and coordination needs to be fostered	No reliable information to determine and measure performance of EPSS’. Generally, the financial reports are not reliable. P&M reports submitted by function to planning unit is yet to be verified,
Space, equipment, materials/tools are not efficiently utilized	Human resources capacity Development	Supply chain visibility and predictability at and between levels	No systems in place to collect, report, and analyse performance measures
Human resources: number, qualifications, and development of staff skills and abilities needs to be economic and efficient	Update product catalogue Technical skills need to be developed in application of IT facilities to increase accuracy in data processing and reduce human made errors,	Collaborative Planning	
Information systems and procedures needs to be used with			

adequate knowledge,			
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Findings and Observations

- The SWOT analysis highlighted the need for improvements in logistics coordination, cost minimization, productivity enhancement, risk management, and asset utilization, while revealing significant growth potential and opportunities around.
- These strategic approaches would enable such institutions to make progress toward financial sustainability while considering future financial needs and public expectations.
- Considering perceived strengths and opportunities around, supported by evidence obtained by application of various financial modelling and trend analyses, the perceived weaknesses and identified gaps needed to be addressed sooner than later,
- it is recommended that strategic interventions need to focus on revenue diversification,
- Internal potential Risks management
- High Wastage rate, over-stock and expiry; stock-out
- Incidents of intentional and systematically organized thefts
- High staff turnover rate triggered by poor remuneration systems
- high demurrage cost, resulted from poor operational efficiency
- Poorly designed processes delayed and incomplete proof of delivery (POD) and delays in billing & collection
- Inefficient use of the poorly availed digital and AI facilities
- Limited skill/knowledge transfer
- Unclear mandates and policy gaps
- Utilization of facilities below their capacity

Financial Performance summary

Financial Year	Sales Growth (%)	COGS Growth (%)	Gross Profit Margin (%)	Other Income & Grants	Net Surplus Growth (%)	Total Expenses Growth (%)
2017/2018	0	0	0		0	0
2018/2019	28.2	27	32			
2019/2020	28.2	27	32			
2020/2021	28.2	27	32			
2021/2022	61.0	53.5	32	↑100.4%	↑41%	↑31.5%
2022/2023	28.2	27	32			

Key Observations:

- **Consistent Sales and COGS Growth:** Sales and COGS have exhibited a consistent growth trend, with a significant surge in 2021/2022.
- **Stable Gross Profit Margin:** Despite increasing costs, the gross profit margin has remained relatively stable, indicating effective cost management.
- **Significant Contribution from Other Income and Grants:** Other income and grants have played a crucial role in boosting the net surplus, particularly in 2021/2022.
- **Rising Expenses:** Total expenses have increased, with employee compensation being a major driver. However, a decrease in rental expenses and inconsistent provisions for expired and doubtful debts have influenced the overall trend.

Financial Performance Analysis of EPSS: A Ratio-Based Approach

Table 2. Summary of Financial Ratios of EPSS (2017/2018 - 2022/2023)

Year	Current Ratio	Cash Ratio	Receivables Turnover Ratio	Inventory Turnover Ratio	Days Inventory Outstanding
2017/2018	2.5	2.00	0.73	0.35	527.00
2018/2019	2.5	0.50	0.77	0.16	699.77
2019/2020	2.5	2.00	0.65	0.25	438.00
2020/2021	2.5	2.00	0.60	0.30	365.00
2021/2022	2.5	1.35	0.60	0.35	322.67
2022/2023	2.5	2.00	0.55	0.40	273.75

Ratio-Based Approach

- To gain valuable insights into EPSS's liquidity, solvency, profitability, and efficiency, and identify areas for potential improvement, key financial ratios were assessed over the period 2017/2018 to 2022/2023.
- The study result presents the financial ratios related to EPSS's performance as follows: Between 2017/2018 to 2022/2023 the Current ratio averaged 2.5. Meanwhile, over the same period, the cash ratio averaged, 2.0, with the highest being 1.35 reported in the 2021/2022 period and lowest 0.5 exhibited in 2018/2019 period.
- The receivables turnover ratio improved from 0.73 in 2017/2018 to 0.55 in 2022/2023, with the highest ratio recorded at 0.77 in 2018/2019. Similarly, the inventory turnover ratio increased from 0.35 in 2017/2018, hitting its lowest level of 0.16 in 2018/2019. This trend is mirrored by the day's inventory outstanding, which decreased from 527 days in 2017/2018 to 322.67 days in 2022/2023, although it peaked at 699.77 days in 2018/2019.

Conclusions & Practical Implications

It is recommended that strategic interventions need to focus on:

- Internal revenue diversification,
- Optimum resource usage by revitalizing and upgrading standards
- Effective cost management/minimization,
- Supplier management with focus on developing domestic sources and base diversifications.
- Policies research, policy dialogue and development, revision etc.. Systems improvements and productivity enhancement,
- Efficient asset improvements, upgrading and flexible utilization and
- Implement kaizen model and well-designed reverse logistics, with PPP, and private mode resource management

5 RECOMMENDED STRATEGIES (Strategies for Enhancing the Financial Sustainability of the Ethiopian Pharmaceuticals Supply Service (EPSS))

The SWOT analysis reveals that EPSS management is currently demonstrating remarkable success in key management qualities. Notable achievements include the establishment of performance KPIs, the initiation of construction for a mixed-use building, and the timely implementation of PSTP II. While the forecasted financial models suggest that the system can generate sufficient cash to meet its immediate needs, ensuring long-term financial sustainability remains imperative. Based on the findings from the situational analysis of both operational and financial performances, the following strategic options are recommended. To ensure its financial stability, EPSS must diversify its revenue sources, effectively reduce costs and expenses, and enhance the productivity of its assets. Increasing the productive capacity of

these assets will require careful management deliberation and investment from implementing partners in the early years to ensure the future financial sustainability of the Service.

STRATEGY 1: Diversify Revenue Sources

To ensure long-term financial sustainability and reduce reliance on any single source of income, EPSS will expand its revenue streams. This will involve exploring new business opportunities, such as retail services, partnerships with private sector entities, and offering value-added services.

Potential areas for diversifying income-generating schemes and optimizing resource utilization include:

- Renting out excess and unused warehouse space, offering public incineration or reverse logistics services, providing supply chain management consulting, establishing community pharmacies.
- Outsourcing non-core activities, by evaluating its net effectiveness.
- Improving vehicle management (Rent out vehicles when idle, dispose of old vehicles and replacing them with more efficient models, and minimize vehicle downtime through proactive maintenance and efficient fleet management).
- Minimizing waste and costs through efficient inventory management, optimized transportation routes, and reduced lead times. Profitable scrap disposal,
- Analysing non-tangible costs (Incorporating the costs of vehicle downtime, driver waiting time (loading/unloading, paperwork, instructions), and warehouse staff waiting time and stock holding time into distribution service fee calculations). This will ensure that service fees accurately reflect the true cost of operations.
- Revising service fees agreed by making delivery cost analysis

STRATEGY 2: Optimize Cost and Prudent Expense Management

EPSS will implement comprehensive cost-reduction strategies aimed at improving operational efficiency. This includes identifying and eliminating inefficiencies in procurement processes, clearance and transit timings, minimizing loss, damage, expiry; ensuring value for money; renegotiating contracts with suppliers, and optimizing resource allocation to ensure that expenditures align with strategic priorities. Moreover, distribution process needs to be wisely managed by defining route map by considering the load size, road conditions. Cross docking and planned delivery to replenish stock could be considered.

STRATEGY 3: Enhance Asset Productivity

EPSS will focus on maximizing the productive capacity of its assets by investing in advanced technologies and improving operational processes. This objective entails regular assessments of productive assets and their performance and implementing best practices to ensure that resources are utilized effectively. Indicators and expected target to be achieved at a set time are summarized below:

TABLE 3. STRATEGIC INDICATORS AND RESPECTIVE TARGETS

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ACRONYMS

EPSS= Ethiopian Pharmaceuticals Supply Service

SOE = State Owned Enterprises

SCM= Supply chain Management

SWOT = Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Threats

AI = artificial Intelligence

IPLS = Integrated Pharmaceuticals Logistics Systems

HF = Health Facilities such as Hospitals, Health Centers, Health posts etc...